

The Process of Conceptualization as a Basis for Categorization

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Abstract: The article gives explanation how the process of conceptualization could be the principal aspect of categorization of a concept. Language, proceeding from its resources, verbalizes this experience only in part. Many differences in the semantic volumes of concepts are determined by one or another socio-cultural context, and socio-cultural stereotypes become "cognitive guidelines" of the category.

Key words: Concept, verbalization, category, conceptualization, categorisation, mental, cognitive, phenomena, linguocognitive.

Conceptualization process is a fundamental cognitive process that forms a cognitive picture of the world. Linguistic meanings as linguistic phenomena, correlated with specific concepts allow us to explore the results of cognition of the phenomena of the surrounding reality. Conceptualization aims at "singling out meaningful units of human experience - structures of knowledge"¹. Russian philosopher S.A. Alekseev in his article "The Concept and the Word" calls "a mental formation that replaces an indefinite set of objects of the same kind for us in the process of thought", a concept defines it as a means of cognizing the surrounding reality.²

In cognitive linguistics, the main direction in which the concept is studied is semantic-cognitive (E.S. Kubryakova, N.N. Boldyrev, Z.D. Popova, A.P. Babushkin, I.A. Sternin, etc.), which considers linguistic means as a material for studying the content of concepts, with subsequent appeal to the national conceptual sphere. As N.N. Boldyrev and other researchers, the concept acts as a unit of knowledge, the result of human knowledge³ or a cognitive scheme that allows organizing or structuring the information received⁴ part of a fragment of the world⁵.

According to E.S. Kubryakova, the concept is defined as a mental operational unit, allocated in the cognitive consciousness in the process of mental activity⁶ or, as S.A. Pesin defines, the concept is a mental image of reality mediated by the subject⁷.

G.G. Slyshkin considers the concept as an element of the consciousness of a person who is in a certain social environment includes a socio-cultural component, which implies the presence in

¹ Alefirenko, N. F. Problemy kognitivnoy lingvistiki / N. F. Alefirenko, N. B. Korina. – Nitra : Izd-vo Un-ta Kirilla i Mefodiya, 2011. – P.216

² Askol'dov S. A. Kontsept i slovo. Russkaya slovesnost'. Ot teorii slovesnosti k strukture teksta. Antologiya. Ed. V. P. Neroznaka. Moscow: Academia, 1997. Pp. 262–269.

³ Boldyrev, N. N. Tipologiya konceptov i yazykovaya interpretatsiya / N. N. Boldyrev // Novaya Rossiya: tradicii i innovatsii v yazyke i nauke o yazyk : materialy dokl. i soobshchenij Mezhdunar. nauch. kon., posvyashch. yubileyu d-ra filol. nauk, prof. L. G. Babenko / otv. red. T. M. Voronina. – Ekaterinburg : Fabrika komiksov, 2016. – P. 18-25.

⁴ Boldyrev, N. N. Kognitivnye skhemy yazykovoy reprezentatsii / N. N. Boldyrev // Voprosy kognitivnoy lingvistiki. – 2016. – № 4. – P. 10-20

⁵ Pimenova, M. V. Tipy konceptov i etapy konceptual'nogo issledovaniya / M. V. Pimenova // Vestnik Kemerovskogo gosudarstvennogo universiteta, – 2013. – № 2 (54), t. 2. – P. 127-131

⁶ Kubryakova, E. S. YAzyk i znanie: na puti polucheniya znanij o yazyke: chasti rechi s kognitivnoy točki zreniya. Rol' yazyka v poznanii mira / E. S. Kubryakova. – Moskva : YAz. slavyan. kul'tury, 2004. – P.560.

⁷ Pesina, S. A. Filosofiya yazyka : ucheb. posobie dlya vuzov / S. A. Pesina. – Moskva : Flinta : Nauka, 2016. – P.376.

the content of the concept of an indication of one or another social value associated with it⁸. The processes of comprehension of reality depend on the emotional and evaluative meaning that the subject attaches to the task set within a specific context with the presence or absence of other members of society in it⁹. This state emphasizes the conditionality of the processes of conceptualization and categorization by the social component that characterizes a person's perception of himself, another and society as a whole¹⁰. The concept as a mental unit can find its expression in the language through various linguistic means, thereby forming a linguistic picture of the world. In this regard, the concept is a linguocognitive phenomenon. The set of lexical units that verbalize the concept constitutes its nominative field. The analysis of lexical meanings that make up the nominative field of language units allows us to explore the content of a linguocognitive phenomenon and reconstruct the cognitive features of a phenomenon or object of reality. Accordingly, meaning is the key to understanding conceptual structures. At the same time, according to Z.D. Popova, it should be noted that it is "the concept that determines the semantics of the linguistic means used to express it" or imposes its meanings on new linguistic forms that have not been used before¹¹. Meanings are mobile and change at the conceptual level for extra-linguistic and intra-linguistic reasons¹². Kolmogorova A.V. understands meaning as "a structure of consciousness that allows a person to connect in a single interaction an object of the surrounding world and a linguistic sign"¹³. The value considered according to I.A. Sternin, as knowledge about an object or phenomenon of the world, expressed through this and fixed by a material shell¹⁴ or, according to V.V. Levitsky, as experimental knowledge about speech and non-speech situations of the possible use of the word¹⁵, conveys only some semantic components of the concept, expressing its "communicatively relevant part"¹⁶. In various communication situations different semantic components or conceptual (cognitive) features are realized, which are distinguished on the basis of the generalization of the meanings of the lexemes of the nominative field of the linguocognitive phenomenon that are close in content to the semantic components. Conceptual (cognitive) features as units of meaning can also be represented by separate word meanings or meaning elements. Modeling of a linguocognitive phenomenon is based on the reconstruction of its cognitive (conceptual) features as reflecting one or another fragment of the external world. In the process of ordering and generalization of cognitive features at a higher level of abstraction, classification features of a linguocognitive phenomenon are formed. The classification feature is interpreted as defining one or another "parameter of the categorization of the corresponding object, phenomenon and generalizing the homogeneous cognitive features of the concept"¹⁷, as well as determining the essential features underlying the category¹⁸. The set of verbalized cognitive features is an ordered structure (field structure), in which the core, near, far and extreme periphery are distinguished, differing in the degree of frequency (brightness index) of the use of certain cognitive features. In modeling the field structure of the linguocognitive phenomena are, the corresponding technique of I.A. Sternin¹⁹ which allows to determine the most relevant and important features of the phenomenon under

⁸ Slyshkin, G. G. Lingvokul'turnye koncepty precedentnykh tekstov v soznanii i diskurse : monografiya / G. G. Ilyshkin ; Mosk. gos. lingvist. un-t. – Moskva : Akademiya, 2000. – P.141.

⁹ Tkachenko, YU. G. Kognitivnye lakuny v soznanii sovremennykh nositelej russkogo i francuzskogo yazykov / YU. G. Tkachenko // Filologicheskij klass. – 2018. – № 4 (54)/. –P. 34-40.

¹⁰ Comportement – Cognition – Cerveau. – URL: http://www.cnrs.fr/comitenational/doc/rapport/2010/27_conj_2010.pdf (дата обращения: 5.11.2018).

¹¹ Popova, Z. D. Oчерki po kognitivnoj lingvistike : kollekt. monografiya / Z. D. Popova, I. A. Sternin ; Voronezh : AST : Istoki, 2001. –189 p.

¹² Metody kognitivnogo analiza semantiki slova : komp'yuterno-korpus. podhod / Ros gos. gumanit. un-t ; pod obshch. red. V. I. Zabolotnoj. – Moskva : YAz.slavyan. kul'tury, 2015. – 344 p.

¹³ Kolmogorova A. V. YAzykovoje znachenie i rechevoj smysl: funkcional'no-semiologicheskoe issledovanie prilagatel'nyh-oboznachenij svetlogo i temnogo v sovremennom russkom i francuzskom yazykah : avtoref-t. dis. ... d-ra filol. nauk : 10.02.19 / A. V. Kolmogorova ; – Kemerovo, 2006. – 38 p.

¹⁴ Sternin, I. A. Leksicheskoe znachenie slova v rechi / I. A. Sternin. – Moskva : Direkt-Media, 2015. – 239 p.

¹⁵ Levickij, V. V. Semasiologiya : monogr. dlya molodykh issledovatelej / V. V. Levickij. – Vinnica : Nova Kn., 2012. – 680 p.

¹⁶ Maklakova, E. A. Teoreticheskie problemy semnoj semasiologii : monografiya / E. A. Maklakova, I. A. Sternin. – Moskva : Direkt-Media, 2015. – 457 p.

¹⁷ Каюмова, Д. Ф. Сравнительная когнитивная лингвистика : крат. конспект лекций / Д. Ф. Каюмова ; Казан. федер. ун-т. – Казань : [б. и.], 2013. – 110 с.

¹⁸ Dzyuba, E. V. Pochemu grusha – eto yagoda v vide yabloka, ili o specifikе nauchnoj i naivnoj kategorizacii v russkoj yazykovoј kartine mira / E. V. Dzyuba // Ural'skij filologicheskij vestnik. Seriya: psiholingvistika v obrazovanii. – 2015. – P. 76-81.

¹⁹ Sternin, I. A. Psiholingvisticheskoe znachenie slova i ego opisanie / I. A. Sternin, A. V. Rudakova. – Moskva : Lambert, 2011. – 192 p.

study. The internal organization of the concept includes informational and interpretive content, as well as the primary sensory image resulting from the knowledge of a fragment of reality by the senses, which is one of the main ways of concept formation²⁰. When constructing a model of a linguocognitive phenomenon, central cognitive features or features of the near/far periphery can include both figurative and informational and interpretive components. Within the framework of the semantic-cognitive approach in the study of concepts, their various types are distinguished, classified on the basis of different grounds. Classification A.P. Babushkina is based on the same analysis of the word, which determines the type of concept: a mental picture (the presence of a figurative seme), a scheme (the presence of a spatial seme), a frame (an archiseme in the design of lexico-semantic groups), a script (the presence of a seme of movement, dynamics), a kaleidoscopic (a set of seme), (image, development, space) and logically constructed (lack of image seme) concepts²¹. The basis of the typology can also be the degree of abstractness of the content, belonging to a specific national community. N.N. Boldyrev distinguishes between types of concepts based on their content and functions. Thematic concepts are considered as the result of the accumulation of knowledge in relation to the cognition of the surrounding reality, and operational ones as mental units, the creation of which is due to various cognitive mechanisms (conceptual metaphor and metonymy, focusing, perspectivization, etc.)²². Scientists also distinguish between conceptually simple (image, scheme, representation, concept, prototype) and conceptually complex formats of knowledge (frame, script, proposition, gestalt, cognitive matrix)²³. Content typology distributes concepts according to the relevant thematic areas or areas of use (individual, household, professional)²⁴. The concept can act as a single cognitive context or area that provides an understanding of the meaning of the word, and, according to the theory of R. Lanecker, manifests itself as the accumulated mental experience of the cognizing subject²⁵. Language, proceeding from its resources, verbalizes this experience only in part. Many differences in the semantic volumes of concepts are determined by one or another socio-cultural context, and socio-cultural stereotypes become "cognitive guidelines" of the category²⁶. Yu.D. Apresyan thinks natural languages demonstrate the specifics of the perception and conceptualization of the world by the people²⁷, being the repository of his experience²⁸. Conceptualization is the basis of categorization, allowing generalization of acquired knowledge based on similar characteristics. Concepts and categories, being mental structures, are inextricably linked with each other. Cognitive linguistics is aimed at studying language as a cognitive ability of consciousness, at the manifestation of cognition through language, considered as the processes of collecting and understanding the information received about the surrounding reality. A number of

A number of researchers are engaged in the possibilities and ways of classifying the knowledge obtained with the help of language categories: A. Vezhbitskaya, J. Lakoff, R. Lanecker, E. Roche, J. Fauconnier, G. Guillaume, F. Rastier, B.-N. Grunig, G. Denhière, D. Dubois, J.-F. Richard, C. Vandeloise, A. Borillo, Arutyunova, O.V. Alexandrova, A.N. Baranov, N.N. Boldyrev, S.G. Vorkachev, V.Z. Demyankov, D.O. Dobrovolsky, A.A. Zalevskaya, V.I. Zabotkina, V.I. Karasik, A.A. Kibrik, V.V. Kolesov, E.S. Kubryakova, V.A. Maslova, Z.D. Popova, E.V. Rakhilina, G.G. Slyshkin, Yu.S. Stepanov, I.A. Sternin, R.M. Frumkina, T.V.

²⁰ Babushkin, A. P. Kognitivnaya lingvistika i semasiologiya : monografiya / A. P. Babushkin, I. A. Sternin. – Voronezh : Ritm, 2018. – 229 p.

²¹ Babushkin, A. P. Kognitivnaya lingvistika i semasiologiya : monografiya / A. P. Babushkin, I. A. Sternin. – Voronezh : Ritm, 2018. – 229 p.

²² Boldyrev, N. N. Kognitivnaya semantika : vved. v kognitiv. lingvistiku : kurs lekcij / N. N. Boldyrev ; Tambov. gos. un-t im. G. R. Derzhavina. – Tambov : Izd-vo TGU, 2014. – 236 p.

²³ Boldyrev, N. N. Kognitivnaya semantika : vved. v kognitiv. lingvistiku : kurs lekcij / N. N. Boldyrev ; Tambov. gos. un-t im. G. R. Derzhavina. – Tambov : Izd-vo TGU, 2014. – 236 p.

²⁴ Boldyrev, N. N. Tipologiya konceptov i yazykovaya interpretaciya / N. N. Boldyrev // Novaya Rossiya: tradicii i innovacii v yazyke i nauke o yazyk : materialy dokl. i soobshchenij Mezhdunar. nauch. kon., posvyashch. yubileyu d-ra filol. nauk, prof. L. G. Babenko / otv. red. T. M. Voronina. – Ekaterinburg : Fabrika komiksov, 2016. –P. 18-25.

²⁵ Langacker, R. Cognitive Grammar: A Basic Introduction / R. Langacker. – Oxford : Oxford University Press, 2008. – 562 p.

²⁶ Boldyrev, N. N. Kognitivnaya semantika : vved. v kognitiv. lingvistiku : kurs lekcij / N. N. Boldyrev ; Tambov. gos. un-t im. G. R. Derzhavina. – Tambov : Izd-vo TGU, 2014. – 236 p.

²⁷ Apresyan, YU. D. Izbrannyye trudy : v 2 t. T. 2. Integral'noe opisanie yazyka i sistemnaya leksikografiya / YU. D. Apresyan. – Moskva : YAz. rus. kul'tury, 1995. – 767 s.

²⁸ Vorkachev, S. G. Lingvokonceptologiya i mezhkul'turnaya kommunikaciya: istoki i celi / S. G. Vorkachev // Filologicheskie nauki. – 2005. – № 4. – S. 76-83.

Chernigovskaya, A.P. Chudinov and others. Various aspects of categorization were studied by such scientists as M.V. Shamanova who developed a comprehensive methodology for studying the communicative category. D.B. Kumakhova singled out the evaluative categorization of reality in the proverbial picture of the world, L.S. Abrosimova described the processes of word-formation categorization, M.N. Konnova studied temporal categorization, I.Yu. Bezukladova reflected on the categorization of space, E.V. Dzyuba analyzed the features of the linguo-cognitive categorization of reality in the Russian linguistic consciousness, Z.A. Manzullina compared gender stereotypes in their linguistic categorization. According to E.S. Kubryakova, cognitive linguistics allows you to explore the language in all its various relationships with human thought and cognitive processes, processes of conceptualization and categorization. One of the ways of forming a cognitive picture of the human world, indicating the processes of cognition, displaying objective reality in the human mind, is categorization or thought processes of recognition, characterized by cognition by analogy, building cause-and-effect relationships between the phenomena of the surrounding world, perceived as a structured whole, comparing not always “for the purposes of cognitive economy”.

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